

ART STUDIES

DEEP SINGING AND DYNAMIC MUSIC - RESEARCH AND INTRODUCTION OF SPANISH "FLAMENCO" ART

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Abstract

Flamenco dance is a special art form that combines song, dance, and guitar performance. Flamenco dance is the music and dance of the Andalusian Gypsies (also known as Flamenco people) in Spain. Originating from the folk songs and dances of Gypsy, Antalusia, Arabia, and Spanish Jews, in the 14th and 15th centuries, Gypsy wanderers brought the Eastern Indian tap dance style and Arab mystical and sentimental charm to Spain in their bold and unrestrained songs and dances.

Keywords: Spain, Music and Dance, Historical Studies, Song and Dance Forms.

Flamenco dance is currently the most popular form of Spanish dance (which is too idealistic, as it is actually the essence of saving Spain. Flamenco means "fleeing farmers," so the most classic and direct understanding is the pounding emotions), and the Spanish are also known for their ability to sing and dance. Flamenco dance is one of the two national treasures of Spain, along with bullfighting. This dance embodies the national culture and characteristics of the Spanish nation. Flamenco dance originated from the common class and expresses the most unreserved emotions of human nature in the movements of dancers. During the performance, there must be a guitar accompaniment and a dedicated person singing alongside. Simultaneously perform impromptu dance. The male dancers on the stage wore tight black pants, long sleeved shirts, and sometimes even a floral vest; The female dance partner combs her hair back into a smooth bun and wears colorful clothing, tight corsets, and a skirt with multiple layers of trim. At the beginning of flamenco dance, the steps are slow, and the male and female partners use their heads and arms to dance in various graceful and arrogant positions. Gradually, the dance steps accelerated, and the musician skillfully fingered out a rapid and ever-changing rhythm. The momentum was like a raging wind and rain, closely following the accelerated dance steps. Suddenly, the guitarist made the last sound on the guitar, and the dancer displayed a beautiful appearance. Everything suddenly came to a sudden stop. The audience often was surprised by the sudden ending, and then couldn't help but cheer and applaud.

The essence of Flamenco is its song, also called "Cantondo", which is often accompanied by guitar music and is Andalusian folk music. In contemporary times, flamenco dance is also undergoing some changes. The dilemma it faces is just like many ancient Chinese art forms face: traditional things are unconsciously losing bit by bit. The flamenco dance is passionate, unrestrained, beautiful, and robust, vividly reflecting the national temperament of the Spanish people. It is also an important source of art for Salzuela. This dance is the best carrier for expressing the love, hate, and sorrow of gypsy girls. This dance has three main elements: accompaniment, accompaniment, and dance, with themes such as God, women, and love. The

key to performing flamenco dance is to pay attention to sufficient coordination between the movements of various parts of the body, either by tapping with feet, or by twirling fingers to make a sound, or by holding a sound-board to tap and dance; The feeling and demeanor of the start, stop, and end movements in each dance sentence, as well as the smooth breathing throughout, are the most challenging parts of flamenco dance. The correct use of the arms requires years of training to truly maintain the relaxation of the arms and upper body while rapidly hitting the ground like raindrops on the heels. It is a perfect unity of technology and art. Flamenco art, known for its passionate and unrestrained spirit, is the most dazzling red on the world art stage. For decades, flamenco artists have performed around the world, igniting the flames of flamenco dance around the world. This flame is constantly stirring people's heartstrings, making people unforgettable.

Flamenco art is a unique genre on the world art stage. The flamenco dance, which represents this art, combines the magnificence of Europe and the unrestrained style of America and is renowned on the world stage. During this period of great change, flamenco dance is also undergoing some changes.

It can be said that the more exquisite an art is, the greater the difficulty of preserving it through generations. Faced with this situation, flamenco dance artists have persistently toured around the world for the development of this art, becoming the Spanish flamenco ballet troupe with the highest number of tours worldwide. As Paco Mora said, "It's not Spain that needs this art the most, but places outside of Spain. Real flamenco dance can only be seen on specialized gypsy stages. Paco Mora and his companions have been trying to give the audience the most authentic flamenco dance in their performances, which is also why they brought the story of the gypsy girl" Carmen "to China.

Although Flamenco was not created by the Gypsies, without them, there would be no Flamenco today; In other words, they are born flamenco performers, with the most hoarse voices and the most complex and varied sense of rhythm. There is a great controversy over where the Gypsies living in Andalusia actually come from; But there is a consensus that they come from northern India and have lived in Persia for a long

time, which is why there are a large number of Persian vocabulary in their language today.

In the late 15th century, gypsies arrived in the Andalusia region of southern Spain. Not long after, they began to face discrimination. Spain passed various laws prohibiting them from engaging in industries other than agriculture, and sent them to mountainous areas, even prohibiting them from speaking their own language - Calo. Jews and Moors were also discriminated against during the same period. For many years, these three types of people have been getting along well, and their respective cultures have been integrated into Flamenco.

Gypsies have a different attitude towards life from others, and in their view, life comes first. When they have to choose between a party and a job, they will not hesitate to choose a party. This attitude of the Gypsies even influenced the majority of Andalusian people. When we say 'don't leave today's work for tomorrow', their views seem to be exactly the opposite. In the 1960s, Spain passed a law requiring bars to close at midnight, as nearly half of the country's population had a happy day until early morning, which seriously affected work efficiency the next day. Throughout Europe, the Gypsies living in Andalusia are perhaps the most closely integrated with society, with many already living a 9-to-5 lifestyle.

In the history of Flamenco, the best performers - whether they were singers, dancers, or guitarists - were mostly gypsies. Even today, it remains the same. For flamenco dancers, dignity is equally important as elegance and skill. This is precisely why all dance performers frown and have no frivolity on their faces. For flamenco dance, there are no strict regulations on movements, and dancers can freely perform according to their own feelings of music. Excellent dancers do not require too much performance space. The focus of female dancers is almost entirely on the movements of the upper body and hands, which are more elegant and smooth. However, male dancers often start by holding their fists tightly and then spreading their fingers to the limit.

The earliest flamenco dances were solo dances, but with the emergence of flamenco performance bands and Tablao, dancers have abandoned the spontaneity of flamenco dance and all movements have been pre-arranged. If you see two or more dancers performing, as long as their movements are exactly the same, it indicates that they have been arranged.

Flamenco dance was originally an improvisation dance. Male dancers have complex dance steps, using their soles, toes, and heels to tap the ground with a lively rhythm; Female dancers follow tradition in their dance steps, mainly showcasing the elegance and elegance of their wrists, arms, and torso. During the performance, the dancers were accompanied by a spontaneous "halo" (i.e. clapping, twirling fingers, and excited shouting). Of course, with the professionalization of flamenco dance, there have been stricter regulations on dancers' moves, and mature dance dramas like Salome have also emerged.

Gypsies grew up in the environment of flamenco dance, and a family of all ages can dance or sing. It's

not too much to say that they have the blood of flamenco (Gypsies often say, "Only gypsies can truly dance flamenco well. The ups and downs, indulgence, and freedom of gypsy life have also presented flamenco dance with freedom, passion, and contradictions. Today, the term flamenco is not only the name of a specific dance, but also used to describe an attitude towards life. According to the dictionary, Flamenco refers to a type of person who pursues pleasure, does not engage in production, is unrestrained, and often lives on the edge of the law. In the minds of artists, "flamenco" is not only a trinity of song, dance, and guitar music, but also represents a generous, passionate, bold, and unrestrained way of life. The popular Bohemian style in the clothing industry in the past two years is a romantic expression of this spirit.

An expert once said, "Flamenco is the dance that enjoys music the most and masters it with the most precision. In flamenco dance, in addition to the accompaniment of songs, guitars, and soundboards, the dancers sometimes clap their hands to the rhythm, and sometimes step on their feet to strengthen the rhythm. With the changes in musical expression, the dancers' physical expressions also become mournful and joyful, as if representing the deepest soul. Throughout the entire performance process, both the artist and the audience are seeking a spiritual connection. Among all dances, the women in flamenco dance are the most alluring. She is not as pure and dignified as the female lead in ballet, nor as passionate and noble as the female partners in national standard dance. She often appears alone, shrugging her shoulders and looking up with a lonely expression in her eyes. In most duet dances, she and the male lead are also close and far apart. When she really started dancing, her expression was still cold and even painful, but her body movements were full of enthusiasm. The soundboard in her hand followed her dance steps with sonorous tones, as if telling her the vicissitudes of her inner past. Isn't this the sexiest picture?

The soundboard is an essential prop for Flamenco's performance. If your ears are very sharp, you can probably hear that the sound produced by the left and right hand soundboards of the dancer is not the same. The sound on the left hand is low and represents a male; The one on the right is more hyperactive and is a female. The harmony of the soundboard in the dancer's hand expresses the dialogue between men and women. To tell the stories of men and women tactfully and beautifully, the talent and life experiences of artists are more important than skills. This is also why many flamenco dancers dance with more flavor as they age. In Shanghai's "The Dance of the River", the flamenco dancer is said to have been dancing for almost 40 years, with obvious fat around her waist. However, when she dances flamenco, you can only think of Duras' cliché - I love your face that has been ravaged by time. The large swing skirt of flamenco dance is also a favorite among women. No matter how fashion trends change, every woman should have such a colorful dance dress in their wardrobe, and there should have been such a night of indulging in dancing with their beloved. Don't think that the flamenco dance dress is too ordinary, and fashion masters don't understand the beauty of human

fireworks. At the 2005 Spring/Summer Jean Paul Gaultier Fashion Show, Gaultier's design was filled with wild and unrestrained elements in details: pleated and wrinkled layers of ruffles, colorful layered floor cake fishtail skirts, etc., combined with avant-garde deconstruction design, presenting both modern and retro post flamenco fashion. And John Galiano, the director of women's clothing creation at Dior, has an extreme style of complexity and extravagance, while his unconventional and vulgar style is outrageous. Who can say that this is not influenced by flamenco dance (his mother is Spanish)?

The characteristic of flamenco dance lies in its unique body language and emotional expression. Dancers convey their inner emotions and emotions through flipping, swinging, and waving their arms, changing footsteps, undulating dance postures, and changing facial expressions. This form of dance relies more on feelings and intuition, and dancers use unique body movements to convey emotions such as anger, sadness, and joy. On stage, flamenco dance exhibits a strong emotional impact, and the audience seems to be able to hear the deep cries of the dancers.

In addition, flamenco dance is closely integrated with flamenco music and singing. Flamenco music is usually accompanied by instruments such as guitars, tambourines, and hand clappers, which work closely with dance to create a unique rhythm and atmosphere. Singing is another important element in flamenco dance, where the singer's passionate singing and the dancers' movements complement each other, making the entire performance more vivid and powerful.

The charm of flamenco dance is not only reflected on stage, but also integrated into the Spanish lifestyle and social culture. In Spain, flamenco dance has become an important national cultural symbol, representing the passion and pride of the Spanish people. Whether at weddings, celebrations, religious festivals, or simple gatherings, flamenco dance is an indispensable part. It not only showcases people's joy and celebration, but also expresses social and personal emotions through dance.

Over time, the influence of flamenco dance has expanded to various parts of the world. More and more countries and regions are offering flamenco dance courses in schools, dance academies, and other places, enabling more people to understand and love this unique form of dance art. Flamenco dance also frequently appears as an important component of international cultural exchange in various dance competitions and cultural festivals, showcasing the diverse cultures of different countries and regions.

In summary, Spanish flamenco dance, as a representative of Spanish dance art, has become a world-renowned art form with its unique emotional expression and body language. It not only carries the emotions and culture of the Spanish people, but also becomes an important link for international cultural exchange. Whether on stage or in life, flamenco dance will continue to illuminate people's hearts and convey strength and hope. This kind of rapid wind and rain, "every time it comes to a halt, waves rise again and again", exudes an inexhaustible vitality, as well as a sense of pride that

can still grasp the rhythm and dance gracefully to protect one's own dignity even when unexpected events constantly strike in life. At this moment, the deep furrowed brow, with its deep sadness and underlying firmness, somewhat made me understand why it used to be the first time for the bottom class refugees to use it to relieve their helpless trivialities.

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